

ISic1276

I.Sicily inscription 1276

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 318

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Φ]οῖβον ἀκερσεκόμην
2. [ἐκ]ατηβόλον Ἀπόλλωνα
3. [ἰ]δρυσάμην σηκ[ῶτ'ἐπὶ]
4. κόσμον κ[αλὸνἔθηκα]
5. Πατρ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

I raised a fine [statue of] long-haired Phoebus, far-shooting Apollo, in a sacred enclosure, and added decoration

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492882

EDCS 39101645

PHI 140765

PHI 316198

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0451 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 8
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5649d
- Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 93

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